

Hybrid Microstrip Device for Hydrogen Detection at Microwave Frequencies

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Abstract—This article describes the analysis, design and construction of a microstrip device capable of detecting hydrogen at microwave frequencies. The proposed structure is a hybrid microstrip line, 10 cm long, having part of the copper line replaced by a strip of palladium film 10 nm thick. A simple formulation has been developed to estimate the device's insertion loss, as well as the spectral dependence of the S_{21} parameter. For a device having a 2 cm long Pd section, exposed to 1.6 % hydrogen at a 0.4 bar pressure in nitrogen gas, detection was accomplished by measuring the changes produced on one of the resonances of the scattering parameter S_{21} in the frequency region around 3.2 GHz. The experimental results, corroborated by the theoretical modeling of the device's response, indicated that, if on one hand, a Pd thickness much smaller than the skin depth, yields a negligible change in attenuation due to hydrogen absorption, on the other, it favors the phase of the S_{21} parameter to become a highly sensitive function of the Pd conductivity, in turn facilitating hydrogen detection. This finding opens the possibility of constructing simple hydrogen sensors by incorporating ultrathin Pd films into planar microwave circuits.

Index Terms—Hydrogen Detection, Microstrip, Palladium, Sensor.

I. INTRODUCTION

CLEAN energy supply is an imminent challenge to current societies. This calls for the development of research aiming to make feasible alternatives to non-renewable energy sources, such as, for example, fossil fuels [1], [2]. In this context, the number of studies using hydrogen as a clean energy

This work was supported in part by CNPq, Brazil (grants: 311625/2019-3 and 142357/2018-9), by CAPES (CAPES-PrInt grants: 88887.311936/2018-00, 88887.571734/2020-00, 88887.370797/2019-00, 88887.568744/2020-00 and 88887.682652/2022-00), by the Secretaria d'Universitats i Recerca del Departament d'Empresa i Coneixement de la Generalitat de Catalunya (IN CERCA grant) and by MCIN, Spain (grant MCIN/AEI/10.13039/50110001103).

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source is increasing, as in refineries, chemical industries, steel mills, food industry and fuel cells [2]–[4].

Hydrogen has a low explosive limit. Concentrations above 4% under atmospheric pressure, make the environment hazardous. For this reason, due to its high relevance as a potential energy source [2], [5], [6], the development of sensors with high detection sensitivity, quick response and operation at room temperature is of great importance [7].

Because the H_2 molecule is extremely small, it can penetrate metallic compounds, placing itself amongst the atoms of the crystal lattice, in turn producing optical, electrical and structural changes in the material [8]. Palladium (Pd) has a specific affinity to hydrogen gas [5], [7], [9]–[12]. In fact, the H_2 molecule dissociates on the surface of the Pd as atomic hydrogen [13], [14], and permeation of H_2 in thin films of Pd leads to the formation of palladium hydrides [15].

There are many reports in the literature directed to hydrogen detection. The most common techniques include the synthesis of new compounds based on palladium, to enhance the detection limit for hydrogen. These generally employ resistive [16], semiconductor [17]–[20], magnetic [21], [22] and optic designs [11], [23]–[25].

Microwave based detection of hydrogen has been less explored. Reports include a technique comprising point detection of hydrogen on a palladium substrate using a microwave probe, as presented by Tabib-Azar and Sutapun [26]. A SIW structure for hydrogen sensing using tin oxide (SnO_2) as a dielectric material is presented by Majid Ndoye *et al.* [27].

The detection principle is based on the effective dielectric permittivity variation when hydrogen is introduced. The work of Adel Benleulmi *et al.* [28] uses passive microwave substrates with an integrated phase shifter that is influenced by the concentration of hydrogen gas. The hydrogen sensor material used is tin oxide (SnO_2) and the phase shift is also influenced by the concentration of hydrogen gas. The work in [26] uses an evanescent microwave probe (EMP) three-dimensional sensor, for hydrogen detection. In EMP, deflections in a Pd -coated cantilever are detected. Stress and resistivity changes in the Pd film are quantified according to hydrogen concentration.

The configuration of the EMP probe used in [26] to detect hydrogen uses moving parts, requires a close and well controlled positioning of the probe relative to the substrate, in turn making it feasible as a bench top measurement approach, but not amenable for wireless reading. The reports in [27] and [28] focus on sensing gases using SIW and tin oxide (SnO_2) and can be configured for wireless sensing. However, the work in [27] requires a complex two side fabrication process, with metallization obtained via holes and the approach is limited in its practical operation, due to the high temperatures required to work effectively (above $200^\circ C$) [29]. In addition, it is important to point out that tin oxide, as used in [27] and [28] can be affected by the presence of other reducing gases, and therefore, these sensors are not specific to hydrogen [30].

In the present work one investigates the transmission spectrum of a simple copper-palladium hybrid configuration on a low-cost FR4 substrate and the changes produced due to exposure to hydrogen. Palladium is used since it has a specific affinity to H_2 and is widely studied in the literature, mostly by use of non-microwave techniques [10], [23]–[25]. Therefore, differently than the schemes used in [27], [28], the proposed measurement approach is not affected by other gases in the environment. The configuration has no moving parts. Device fabrication is simple and with low-cost and sensor operation is at room temperature. It is demonstrated that use of a strip section of ultrathin Pd film in the hybrid microwave structure is suitable for hydrogen detection, a result that would appear unexpected at a first glance, given that in this case, the film thickness is much smaller than the skin depth. This is an important finding, as thin film deposition and patterning of Pd by consolidated methods of sputtering or electron beam evaporation is widespread and allows for large scale fabrication at low-cost. This feature together with the well established use of radio frequency identification (RFID) and planar patch antenna systems, operating at microwave frequencies, allows for the development of simple sensor heads that can serve as unit cells in wireless sensor networks for hydrogen detection.

II. PRELIMINARY ANALYSIS

As reported by Tabib-Azar and Sutapun [26], the resistivity of Pd increases by about 13.5% under exposure to H_2 in a concentration of 3% (volume/volume) in the surrounding ambient. This corresponds to a similar relative reduction in conductivity, directly related to the swelling of palladium upon exposure to hydrogen. According to reports in the literature, an approximate increase in linear dimension of approximately

TABLE I
PARAMETERS OF THE FABRICATED DEVICES

Parameter	Value
Total device length L , mm	100
Pd section lengths x , mm	20, 40
Microstrip width w , mm	2.9
Microstrip height h , mm	1.53
Cu thickness t , mm	0.035
Pd conductivity σ , S/m	9.5×10^6
Pd thickness y , nm	10
Device width k , mm	70
FR4 approximate relative permittivity ϵ [34]	4.2

3.5% can occur when palladium is exposed to 4% hydrogen. [31], [32]. The two effects are related, as a larger volume of material yields a lower concentration of free carriers. A substantial change in conductivity can also be obtained for specially prepared palladium nanoparticles that fail to form a continuous film on a flat substrate. Swelling, due to exposure to hydrogen causes the formation of bridges and new contacts between particles, which increases the conductivity by as much as 68% upon exposure to 2% hydrogen [32].

The design proposed for the device, as illustrated in Fig. 1, is a hybrid microstrip configuration in which a longitudinal section of length x of the copper line is replaced by a palladium film with thickness y . This palladium section works as an active part of the sensor. A microstrip configuration was chosen for the sake of simplicity for both its design and manufacture. The device was projected so that the impedance of the copper section was 50Ω [33], thus chosen to match the impedance of the network analyzer used in the experiments. Table I lists the relevant parameters of the fabricated devices.

A. Effects on the Attenuation of the Pd Line

Changes in the palladium conduction properties have an effect on both the insertion loss of the device and on specific resonances in the transmittance spectrum. These resonances are expected as a result of the discontinuities in the copper/palladium junctions and on the guiding properties of the palladium region of the device. In this section a preliminary analysis of the effect on the insertion loss of the palladium line is provided. Effects due to field spreading and resonances are discussed in Section II-B.

Given that the palladium thickness in the proposed design is small relative to the skin depth of the metal, one important question is to estimate the dependence of the transmitted signal to changes in the palladium parameters. Assuming a

Fig. 1. Hybrid microstrip structure and project parameters.

simple model, with a TEM wave propagating in the Pd section shown in Fig. 1, for an unitary microwave H -field, the power dissipated ΔP in a longitudinal length Δx of the Pd section can be determined using the concept of sheet resistance [35]. For a finite thickness y one obtains

$$\Delta P = w\Delta x \frac{R_s}{2} (1 - e^{-2y/\delta_s}), \quad (1)$$

with

$$R_s = \frac{1}{\sigma\delta_s}, \quad (2)$$

representing the sheet resistance, and

$$\delta_s = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi f \mu_0 \sigma}}, \quad (3)$$

the skin depth in the Pd film. In (3), $\mu_0 = 4\pi \times 10^{-7}$ H/m is the vacuum permeability, f is the frequency and σ is the Pd conductivity.

An estimate for the attenuation constant is obtained by considering the power flowing on the strip having height h and width w , here approximated by an uniform power distribution. The power P_0 flowing through the line, for the unitary H -field is approximately [35]

$$P_0 = \frac{1}{2} Zwh, \quad (4)$$

with

$$Z = \sqrt{\frac{\mu_0}{\epsilon}} \quad (5)$$

representing the wave impedance of the Pd strip section and ϵ , the FR4 relative permittivity. The attenuation constant α is obtained by assuming the transmitted power of the form

$$P = P_0 e^{-\alpha x}, \quad (6)$$

which corresponds to the condition

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{P_0} \frac{\Delta P}{\Delta x}. \quad (7)$$

Using (1) and (4) in (7), one obtains

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{h} \frac{R_s}{Z} \left(1 - e^{-2y/\delta_s}\right). \quad (8)$$

For $y \ll \delta_s$, a first order approximation of this expression yields

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{h} \frac{2y}{\delta_s} \frac{R_s}{Z}. \quad (9)$$

By use of (2) and (3), this expression can be written in the form

$$\alpha = \frac{2\pi f \mu_0}{hZ} y. \quad (10)$$

Thus, to first order, the attenuation constant is independent of the metal conductivity, increases linearly with both the frequency and the metal film thickness. As mentioned earlier a thickness change can be produced by H_2 adsorption. The effect on the magnitude of transmittance, defined by

$$T \equiv |S_{21}|^2 = e^{-\alpha x}, \quad (11)$$

can be determined by using a first order approximation for the exponential factor, resulting in the relation

$$\Delta T = -(\alpha x)y, \quad (12)$$

with α given by (10).

For $y \gg \delta_s$ (8) yields

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{h} \frac{R_s}{Z}. \quad (13)$$

By use of (2) and (3) into (13), one obtains

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{h} \frac{1}{Z} \sqrt{\frac{\pi f \mu_0}{\sigma}}. \quad (14)$$

Thus, the attenuation constant increases with the square root of the conductivity. By use of this last expression in conjunction with (11), the fractional change in transmittance can be cast in the form

$$\frac{\Delta T}{T} = \frac{\alpha x}{2} \frac{\Delta \sigma}{\sigma}. \quad (15)$$

Thus, the fractional change in transmittance is a factor αx times the corresponding fractional change in conductivity.

For an arbitrary palladium thickness, one has to take into account the changes in both the conductivity and thickness due to hydrogen adsorption. As discussed in the beginning of this section, the palladium conductivity decreases with increasing hydrogen adsorption, while the linear dimension increases. For a fractional change in thickness $\Delta y/y$ a corresponding change in conductivity

$$\frac{\Delta \sigma}{\sigma} = -\kappa \frac{\Delta y}{y}, \quad (16)$$

occurs. Based on the experimental observations reported in [26], [31], [32], $\kappa \approx 3$ to 4. In this case, the fractional change in transmittance can be cast in the form

$$\frac{\Delta T}{T} = \frac{\partial T}{\partial \sigma} \Delta \sigma + \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \Delta y. \quad (17)$$

By use of (11), with the help of (2), (3), (8) and (16), after a few algebraic manipulations, yields

$$\frac{\Delta T}{T} = \frac{x}{2h} \frac{R_s}{Z} g(y) \frac{\Delta \sigma}{\sigma}, \quad (18)$$

with

$$g(y) \equiv 1 - \left[1 + 2 \frac{y}{\delta_s} \left(1 - \frac{2}{\kappa}\right)\right] e^{-2y/\delta_s} \quad (19)$$

Fig. 2 shows a plot of the g function, given by (19), with and without inclusion of the interdependence (16). The interdependence can be neglected by setting $\kappa \rightarrow \infty$ in (19). The value $\kappa = 3$ in the simulation, corresponds to the variation produced in the volume for a given change in linear dimension. The plots show differences for thicknesses around the skin depth, and they are not important for $y \gg \delta_s$. A few remarks can be drawn from this preliminary analysis, useful to predict what effect hydrogen adsorption would produce on the insertion loss of the device. For small thickness, the transmittance changes linearly with the thickness. However, as indicated in (9), a measurable transmittance change would only be observable for an unrealistic long section of the sensitive strip. A better approach is to design the device with $y \gg \delta_s$. As indicated in (18), for $g = 1$, and noticing that for palladium $R_s \ll Z$, the relative transmittance change due to a relative change in conductivity can only be increased by raising the ratio x/h . For example, for the device investigated in this work, for the case of palladium, one obtains from (18),

for a 1 m long section of palladium metal, $\Delta T/T \approx 2\%$ for $\Delta\sigma/\sigma = 13.5\%$. The effect would be very small to be observed in the device investigated in the present work. An observable effect, however, can occur if resonances are present in the device, as discussed in the following section.

B. Field Spreading and Resonances due to Discontinuities

For two strip lines having one intermediate strip having a thickness much smaller than the skin depth, as in the proposed design, important effects may occur. First, as the intermediate section is weakly guiding, the incoming guided wave exiting the first Cu line, tends to spread transversely as it penetrates in the Pd section. The field amplitude at the input of the second copper section is thus substantially smaller. A second effect, given the fact that the intermediate Pd section is very lossy and highly mismatched to the first line (due to spreading), is a high reflection coefficient at each Cu/Pd discontinuity. This partial reflection coefficient is complex (because of the lossy Pd line) and its phase may change as a function of the Pd thickness. The thicker is the Pd film in the intermediate section, the lower is the Cu/Pd reflection coefficient and the less is the spreading effect, and vice-versa. As discontinuities cause both constructive and destructive resonances, it is expected that changes in the conductivity (and thickness) of the intermediate section can cause shifts in the resonances that can be more dominant than the effect produced by attenuation itself.

In the following semi-quantitative analysis, one first estimates the amount of loss due to field spread in the Pd section. Then, one includes this effect on the overall transmittance function of the device, and also analyze the modifications that could be produced on this function by phase changes in each of the Cu/Pd discontinuities.

1) *Spreading effect on the Pd section:* Fig.3 shows the geometrical construction for performing the analysis of the overall transmittance function of the device. It is assumed that the single interface reflection coefficients at the input and at the first Cu/Pd discontinuities are r_{in} and r , respectively, with

$$r = |r| \exp(j\phi), \quad (20)$$

with ϕ representing a phase factor due to the Cu/Pd discontinuity. Notice that the reflection coefficient at the second Pd/Cu junction is minus the first one, as well as the exit junction reflection coefficient, relative to the device's input coefficient. At each reference plane indicated in Fig.3, the corresponding input reflection coefficient is Γ_i , with $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$. Notice also that $\Gamma_4 = -r_{in}$.

Given that the width of the Cu line is w , and assuming a very weakly guiding Pd section, it is expected that the field within this section spreads horizontally. For $\lambda_g = \lambda/\sqrt{\epsilon} \approx w$ ($\lambda =$ free space wavelength) one expects an estimated diffraction angle obtained from the condition $\sin\theta \approx \lambda_g/w$ [36]. In the present case, at the highest frequency of 8 GHz, $\lambda_g \approx 20$ mm. Given that $w = 2.9$ mm, the condition $\lambda_g \gg w$ is satisfied. In this case, the Cu/Pd junction behaves as a small aperture radiator and under this condition, the field spreads, approximately in a cylindrical wavefront in the far field, as illustrated in Fig.3. Even though the far field condition is not rigorously satisfied, given that $x \approx \lambda_g$, a cylindrical wavefront is assumed for a first-order estimate of the spreading effect. Thus, if E is the field at the input of the Pd section and E' is the field at the second Pd/Cu junction, power conservation implies [36]

$$E^2 wh = E'^2 2\pi x h. \quad (21)$$

This corresponds to an amplitude transmission factor due to diffraction given by

$$t_D = \sqrt{\frac{w}{2\pi x}} \quad (22)$$

For example, for the projected device, $w = 2.9$ mm and for the case $x = 20$ mm, one has $t_D = 0.15$, which yields a power transmittance of -16.4 dB.

One takes into account the fact that this effect disappears as the Pd thickness becomes much larger than the skin depth, by a phenomenological modification of (22) to the form

$$\tau_D = 1 - (1 - t_D) e^{-\frac{y}{\delta_s}}. \quad (23)$$

In this expression, the transmission coefficient becomes unitary as the Pd thickness y is much larger than the Pd skin depth δ_s , and for $y = 0$, one has $\tau_D = t_D$.

2) *Device transmittance function:* The transmittance function can be calculated taking into account the multiple reflections and transmissions in the device. According to [37], and neglecting the diffraction effect, the transmission factor can be cast in the form

$$\tau = e^{-j\beta L} e^{-\alpha x/2} \prod_{m=1}^4 \frac{1 - r_m \Gamma_m}{1 - r_m}, \quad (24)$$

with $r_1 = r_{in}$, $r_2 = r$, $r_3 = -r$ and $r_4 = -r_{in}$. The reflection coefficient at the m -th reference plane is [37]

$$\Gamma_m = \frac{r_m + \Gamma_{m+1} e^{-j2\beta d_m}}{1 + r_m \Gamma_{m+1} e^{-j2\beta d_m}}. \quad (25)$$

Fig. 2. Function g for $\kappa = 3$ and for $\kappa \rightarrow \infty$.

In (25) $\beta_1 = \beta_3 \approx 2\pi/\lambda_g$ and $\beta_2 \approx -j\alpha/2 + 2\pi/\lambda_g$. Thicknesses that appear in the exponential term in (25) are given by $d_1 = d_3 = (L - x)/2$ and $d_2 = x$. To calculate the transmission factor in (24), (25) is calculated in the sequence $m = 3, 2, 1$ with $\Gamma_4 = -r_{in}$.

To include the spreading effect represented by the transmission factor τ_D given by (23), the following procedure is done: (a) the transmission coefficient τ_D enters as a multiplicative factor in front of the overall transmission coefficient (24); (b) in the expression for the reflection coefficient Γ_2 within the Pd section, the squared of the transmission factor is applied in all exponential factors that appear in the coefficient. This is done because the interference term in the reflection coefficient is a round trip factor. Doing this procedure, the coefficient Γ_2 is modified to the form

$$\Gamma_2 = \frac{r_2 + \tau_D^2 \Gamma_3 e^{-\alpha x - j2\beta x}}{1 + \tau_D^2 r_2 \Gamma_3 e^{-\alpha x - j2\beta x}}. \quad (26)$$

With these modifications, the device's S_{21} parameter assumes the form

$$S_{21} = \tau_D^2 e^{-j\beta L} e^{-\alpha x/2} \prod_{m=1}^4 \frac{1 - r_m \Gamma_m}{1 - r_m}, \quad (27)$$

with Γ_1 and Γ_3 obtained from (25) and Γ_2 calculated from (26).

3) *Simulation of the influences of the field spreading and phase on the device transmittance*: In order to estimate to what degree the spreading and phase changes in the reflection coefficient r affect the transmittance spectrum, parameters were adjusted so that the transmittance range within the measured frequency spectrum was approximately that observed experimentally, as detailed in Section IV. For the measured device having $x = 20$ mm, this range was between approximately -27 and -55 dB. To be able to choose a proper set of parameters, a Mathematica® [38] script was written, to study the interdependence of (27) on the several parameters. This study was greatly facilitated by use of the *Manipulate* built-in function of Mathematica®. One thus chose the set of parameters shown in Table II. The non-hydrogenated Pd conductivity was set at the value tabulated in the literature

Fig. 3. Geometrical construction for the analysis of the transmittance function. In the figure: r = single interface reflection coefficient at the Cu/Pd interface. Parameters Γ_m , $m = 1, 2, 3, 4$, are the input reflection coefficients at each reference plane. Parameter S_{21} is the overall transmission factor.

TABLE II
PARAMETER VALUES USED IN THE SIMULATIONS

Parameter	Value
r_{in}	0.49
$ r $	0.83
Start value of the phase parameter $\phi = \phi_0$, rad	0.5
Start value of Pd conductivity σ , S/m	9.5×10^6
Start value of the Pd thickness y , nm	10
Length of the Pd section x , mm	20
$\Delta\sigma$ due to hydrogen absorption	-13.5%
Δy due to hydrogen absorption	+3.5%
Assumed phase change $\Delta\phi$, mrad	10

at 293 K [39], namely, $\sigma = 9.5 \times 10^6$ S/m. The frequency dependence of the FR4 permittivity was that measured by Holzman [34], given by the 3rd degree fitting polynomial function

$$\epsilon = 0.0002462f^3 - 0.006278f^2 + 0.02455f + 4.1752. \quad (28)$$

Fig. 4 shows the frequency dependence of the magnitude of the S_{21} parameter, for the starting parameter values in Table II. As can be noticed from the plot, there are constructive and destructive interferences within the simulated frequency range. For the choice of parameters listed in Table II, there are 4 maxima and 3 minima, but these numbers could be switched, depending on the starting value of the phase parameter ϕ_0 . These correspond to interference effects related to the characteristic strip lengths (due to the several junctions of the device), $\Delta L = 20, 40, 60$ and 100 mm. The variation range of the S_{21} parameter is between -25 and -60 dB, which is close to that measured experimentally.

Fig. 5 shows the effect of changing the Pd film parameters (thickness and conductivity), due to a hypothetical adsorption of hydrogen, as listed in Table II. In this plot, the plotted function is defined as the change in S_{21} parameter

$$\Delta S_0 \equiv 20 \log \left(\frac{|S_{21h}|}{|S_{21}|} \right) \quad (29)$$

with S_{21} and S_{21h} representing the non-hydrogenated and hydrogenated cases, respectively. Notice from the curves plotted in Fig. 5, that the spreading effect greatly enhances the device sensitivity, relative to that due to attenuation alone. This small sensitivity of the attenuation parameter had already been anticipated in Section II-A. Even so, the large sensitivity increase in transmittance at midband of ≈ 0.017 dB is rather small for hydrogen detection.

Fig. 6 shows a plot of the spectral dependence of the function

$$\Delta S_1 \equiv 20 \log \left(\frac{|S_{21h}(\phi_0 + \Delta\phi)|}{|S_{21}(\phi_0)|} \right) \quad (30)$$

corresponding to the effect of changing both the Pd film parameters (thickness and conductivity due to hydrogen absorption) with inclusion of the spreading effect, and the starting phase parameter $\phi = \phi_0 = 0.5$ rad, as listed in Table II, by a very small amount $\Delta\phi = 10$ mrad. This phase change is about 2% of the starting phase ϕ_0 , and therefore much smaller than the 13.5% relative change in Pd conductivity due to hydrogen absorption, as measured in [26]. As can be noticed

Fig. 4. Simulated spectral dependence of the S_{21} parameter for the starting parameter values listed in Table II.

from the plot the phase effect produces a much larger variation in the transmitted spectrum with a typical value which is approximately 25 times larger than that due to the isolated beam spreading effect.

It is important to point out that due to the extremely thin Pd film used in the fabricated devices (10 nm), the conductivity and swelling of Pd may change by a much higher percentage than that assumed in the simulations [32]. Therefore, relative changes in the spectral response of the transmittance function may be much higher than that estimated in the plot of Fig.6.

Even though one cannot determine at this point the exact influence of Pd film parameters on the phase of the Pd/Cu reflection coefficient, this detailed semi-quantitative analysis, taking into account the several factors that may influence the device response, can be used as a basis for interpretation of the measured response of the studied devices, as described in more detail in Section IV. It is important to point out that other effects that might be present were not included as they would add complexity to the analysis, as for example, interference effects due to leakage near the device edges, from the weak guiding in the Pd section, losses in the dielectric substrate and intrinsic insertion loss of the fabricated devices. These may add additional resonance and modulation effects on the S_{21} spectrum as shown in more detail in Sections III and IV.

III. DEVICES AND EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

A. Devices and Gas Cell

The microstrip devices were fabricated on a double-sided, copper coated, FR4 laminate patterned by photolithography. Device dimensions are those listed in Table I. Detection of H_2 is carried out by measuring changes in the scattering parameter S_{21} in the frequency range from 1 GHz to 8.5 GHz when the structure is exposed to hydrogen.

After defining the parameters, simulations of several device configurations, with and without the Pd section were performed using the HFSS (High Frequency Structure Simulator) software [40]. Fig. 7 illustrates the layout of the hybrid microstrip device. For palladium metallization, a sputtering deposition machine was used. An adhesive copper mask was placed on the strip side of the substrate, such as to leave

Fig. 5. Simulated spectral dependence of the ΔS_0 parameter due to changes in the Pd film as listed in Table II with and without the inclusion of the spreading effect within the Pd section of the device.

Fig. 6. Simulated spectral dependence of the ΔS_1 parameter due to the hydrogen induced changes in the Pd film and assuming a 10 mrad phase change in the Cu/Pd reflection coefficient, as listed in Table II.

Fig. 7. Layout of the projected device: (a) Microstrip structure, with copper line. (b) Hybrid microstrip structure after sputtering a length x with Pd .

exposed just the section of the substrate board where the palladium was to be deposited. Sputtering of the metal was done by using a high vacuum laboratory system PLS 500 [41]

with a vacuum pressure of 3 mTorr and an evaporation rate of 9.57 nm/min. For this method of deposition it is too costly to deposit films having thicknesses larger than approximately 30 nm. In the experimental runs carried out, one was only able to fabricate reliable devices with the *Pd* film having 10 nm in thickness.

Fig.8a shows photographs of the devices, right after metallization, still with the copper masks. The *Pd* deposited region appears over a circular area on each device. After metallization and mask removal, one obtained the devices illustrated in Fig. 8b. Any excess of *Pd* deposited on top of the copper line, as occurred with the 20 mm device, as illustrated in Fig. 8b, were expected not to interfere with the transmission properties, because the Cu thickness was much larger than the corresponding skin depth for copper. Two microstrip structures were manufactured, with $x = 20$ mm and $x = 40$ mm, both with $y = 10$ mm.

As shown in Fig. 9, a sealed gas cell was built to allow gas delivery as well as to keep the active sensor at a constant pressure during measurements. The gas cell was designed in such a way that only the section containing palladium would come into contact with hydrogen. For this purpose two acrylic protection pieces were built, one lower and one upper, with the purpose not only to keep the sensor fixed between the two parts with the help of screws, but also to compress an O-ring that sealed the device against leakage to the environment.

B. Experimental Setup

After fabrication, the sensors were ready to be exposed to a standard mixture of H_2 diluted in N_2 . Measurements were carried out by use of the setup shown in Fig. 10. The experiments are run by use of a gas delivery system comprising a pure nitrogen gas cylinder and a hydrogen cylinder in a balance of nitrogen with relative concentrations of 4% and 96% respectively, for a nominal pressure of 1 bar.

A system controller is employed to allow gas flow at a controlled pressure to the gas cell assembly. While the sensor is being exposed to hydrogen and nitrogen gases at a constant pressure, measurements are taken by use of a vector network

Fig. 8. (a) Sputtered devices with the adhesive copper masks showing the footprint of the palladium deposit, (b) Hybrid microstrip structure, after removal of the masks.

Fig. 9. Microstrip device and gas cell.

Fig. 10. Hydrogen detection system. (1) Gas delivery system, (2) sensor/gas cell assembly, (3) vector network analyzer, (4) computer.

analyzer after a SOLT —short, open, load, thru— calibration with the data stored in a computer. Subsequently, after the sensor is exposed to the gases, these gases are purged from the cell, which is filled with pure nitrogen. During the experiments, the pressure was kept at 0.4 bar, either when the cell was filled with nitrogen or with the hydrogen mixture. Thus, for the hydrogen mixture, the final concentration was 1.6%.

IV. RESULTS

A. Preliminary Characterization of Devices

Two copper microstrip lines of lengths $L = 40$ mm and $L = 100$ mm were built for carrying out measurements without the presence of any gases. This was done for three main purposes, namely: to verify the impedance matching of the structure with a vector network analyzer; to examine the microstrip size influence on the insertion loss; and to compare the simulated and measured results for the S_{21} parameter so as to observe the FR4 loss tangent behavior with respect to frequency.

Fig. 11 shows plots of the frequency dependence of the measured and simulated S_{21} parameters for the two copper lines. As can be observed from the plots, there is an increase in the measured attenuation for $f > 5$ GHz, not predicted in

Fig. 11. Measured and simulated frequency dependence of the S_{21} parameter for a copper stripline.

the simulations, for both devices. The increased attenuation is not related to the size, as both devices showed similar responses regarding this parameter. It is expected that the microstrip transmission line cross section starts to propagate higher order modes as frequency increases resulting in higher losses compared to the simulation that assumes a pure quasi-TEM wave only. Based on this preliminary analysis, the frequency range $1 \text{ GHz} < f < 5 \text{ GHz}$ was adopted as the main spectral window for characterization of the hybrid devices, as no significant attenuation was expected to occur due to higher order mode propagation through the microstrip cross section, in this frequency range.

Fig.12 shows a comparison between simulations of the S_{21} parameters for the 100 mm copper stripline and for the copper (40 mm)-palladium (20 mm)-copper (40 mm) hybrid line, along with the measured S_{21} parameter for the copper line. This plot shows that the HFSS simulation only predicts a larger drop in transmittance for the hybrid line, with a smooth reduction in transmittance as a function of frequency with no resonance features (observed experimentally, as detailed in the next paragraph). This is very likely due to the fact that the HFSS simulator did not take into account radiation losses, higher order modes and other effects due to connectors, soldering etc. Because of this, one decided to evaluate the problem analytically as described in Section II-B, to understand the modulation introduced by reflections and resonances present in the proposed structure.

Fig. 13 shows spectra of the hybrid devices for $x = 20$ and $x = 40$ mm, both before exposure to H_2 . The observed insertion losses at the low frequency edge is in the order of 28 dB and 56 dB for $x = 20$ and $x = 40$, respectively. At the high-frequency edge the insertion losses of both devices are similar and in the order of 27 dB. From the discussion in Section II-A this high insertion loss is not from the attenuation of the Pd microstrip, as the thickness is much smaller than the skin depth. As anticipated in Section II-B, this high insertion loss is the result of the weak guiding in the Pd microstrip section, as well as to a high mismatch between field

Fig. 12. Simulated and measured frequency dependencies of the S_{21} parameter for the 100 mm copper stripline. Also shown is the simulated frequency dependence of the S_{21} parameter for the copper(40 mm)-palladium(20 mm)-copper(40 mm) hybrid line.

Fig. 13. Insertion loss for the devices with Pd parameters $x = 20$ mm, 40 mm and $y = 10$ nm with N_2 , at 0.4 bar.

distributions on the copper and thin palladium lines. This also explains the resonance dips in both spectra, as indicated in the detailed analysis of Section II-B.

B. Hybrid Microstrip Device with $x = 20$ mm

For the hybrid device having $x = 20$, each experiment was done at a constant pressure of 0.4 bar. The device was exposed firstly to nitrogen for 5 minutes, then a measurement of S_{21} was made. After the first measurement a vacuum was made throughout the system to remove the N_2 and expose the device to H_2 for 20 minutes. After this first run, the procedure was repeated and a second measurement of the device after a 20-minute exposure to hydrogen was carried out. One did not keep repeating the measurements to avoid the irreversible formation of palladium hydrides [15] with subsequent loss of response from the devices. These two measurements served to determine whether the device could reproduce its response, relative to the noise level measured in the system.

Measurements indicated that the S_{21} parameter was affected upon exposure of the device to 1.6% H_2 , relative to the

Fig. 14. Insertion loss response after exposure to both N_2 and H_2 , for $x = 20$ mm.

signal obtained for pure N_2 in the cell. These results are shown in Fig. 14, only for the first run, for the sake of clarity. The plots shown in the figure indicate that for $f < 5$ GHz, noticeable differences occur for the measured spectra. Based on this observation, for a better analysis, the difference between spectra, measured before and after device exposure to 1.6% H_2 was calculated by defining the parameter

$$\Delta S \equiv 10 \log(T_h) - 10 \log(T_n) = 10 \log\left(\frac{T_h}{T_n}\right), \quad (31)$$

with T_h and T_n representing the magnitude squared of the S_{21} parameter, as defined in (11), for the device exposed to hydrogen and nitrogen, respectively. To determine whether or not the measured spectrum of ΔS was due to any external effect not related to hydrogen absorption, such as noise due to poor shielding, or other type of noise, the uncertainty of the measurements was determined. For this, five measurements were performed on the device, with the cell exposed to nitrogen at 0.4 bar. A time gap of 5 minutes was used between measurements. From this sequence of 5 measurements, one calculated the parameter

$$\Delta S' \equiv 10 \log \frac{T_i}{T_j}, \quad (32)$$

with $i, j = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, i \neq j$, representing the measurement index, i.e., the difference between any two spectra for the nitrogen exposed device. This definition is similar to those of (29) and (30). Neglecting the sign of the differences this combination yields 10 spectra for $\Delta S'$.

Fig. 15 shows the spectra of ΔS for the two experimental runs of hydrogen measurements, plotted together with the 10 spectra of $\Delta S'$. It is possible to observe that for frequencies of approximately 2.10 GHz, 3.20 GHz and 4.70 GHz, the parameter ΔS has a magnitude well distinguished from the maximum noise $\Delta S'$. For the frequency range around 3.20 GHz, the signal ΔS for both runs of hydrogen measurements, is clearly well above the noise level at any frequency of the entire spectrum, thus demonstrating that the device can specifically detect hydrogen. It is important to point out

Fig. 15. Frequency dependence of the signal ΔS and of the uncertainty parameter $\Delta S'$, for $x = 20$ mm.

that, according to the analysis of Section II-B.2, the changes observed experimentally would be due to hydrogen induced phase changes in the reflection coefficient at each Cu/Pd junction.

C. Hybrid Microstrip Device with $x = 40$ mm

For the $x = 40$ mm device, the measurement process and the gas exchange routine at a constant pressure of 0.4 bar were identical to those employed for the $x = 20$ device, and two experimental cycles of hydrogen measurement were carried out, as well. Fig. 16 shows the spectra measured prior and after the first exposure to 1.6% H_2 , with some differences observed for $f < 5$ GHz. Both runs of hydrogen measurements gave very similar values, i.e., both exhibited differences relative to the spectrum measured under exposure to pure nitrogen, that were not as clearly noticeable as those observed for the $x = 20$ device.

To determine if the observed signals could be distinguishable from noise, one repeated the procedure outlined in the previous section, i.e., again five measurements were performed 5 minutes apart thus forming the combination of 10 spectra for $\Delta S'$, as defined in (32).

Fig. 17 shows one of the spectra of ΔS plotted together with the 10 spectra of $\Delta S'$. It is possible to observe that for frequencies around 1.20 GHz and 2.60 GHz, the spectra ΔS exhibits significant amplitudes. However, the noise spectrum exhibits amplitude values even larger than the maximum amplitude of ΔS , considering the entire spectrum. This comparison shows that this device does not perform well compared to the device with the shorter Pd line length. This is probably a result of much larger field spreading caused by the long active layer, relative to that with $x = 20$.

D. Estimated Detection Limit and Comparison with Alternative Techniques

In Table III we make a direct comparison of the estimated detection limit obtained in this work, for the $x = 20$ mm device, relative to those from studies in the literature directed to

Fig. 16. Insertion loss response after the exposure to both N_2 and H_2 , for $x = 40$ mm.

Fig. 17. Frequency dependence of the signal ΔS and of the uncertainty parameter $\Delta S'$, for $x = 40$ mm.

detecting hydrogen using microwave techniques. The general measurement approach for each technique, is ordered from 1 to 4 in Table III. As already outlined in Section I, in approach 1 an evanescent microwave probe is used to detect resistivity and volume changes on a palladium layer due to hydrogen. In approach 2, a substrate integrated waveguide resonator is employed with a SnO_2 powder transducer, whereby one measures shifts in the resonance frequency upon exposure of the transducer to hydrogen. Approach 3 is similar to approach 2, but phase shifts are measured instead. Finally, approach 4 is the one explored in the current work. For approach 2, measurements were carried out with a constant hydrogen concentration of 2% and no detection limit was determined.

As noticed from Fig.15, the noise level represented by the parameter $\Delta S'$ has a maximum magnitude of 3 dB while the signal ΔS has an approximate magnitude of 9 dB. A conservative detection limit for hydrogen with the current configuration would then be the working concentration of hydrogen of 1.6%, which corresponds to the dB level in which the signal $|\Delta S|$ is about 3 times the noise level $|\Delta S'|$. This is

TABLE III
DETECTION LIMITS FOR A NUMBER OF MICROWAVE TECHNIQUES USED TO DETECT HYDROGEN

Reference	[26]	[27]	[28]	This work
Measurement approach	1	2	3	4
Frequency range, GHz	0.01–1.05	4 – 6	6.9 – 7.6	1 – 8.5
H_2 detection limit, %	0.1	2	0.1	1.6

the criterion used to list the detection limit of the current work in the table.

As can be noticed in Table III, the detection limit obtained with the simple configuration explored in this work is higher than that estimated for the other approaches —except for the case of approach 2, for which no detection limit was determined. Even so, for a number of applications, such as those directed to detecting explosive hydrogen levels in mines and in oil extraction fields, the detection limit obtained with the simple device configuration of the current work would be very good in practice. It is important to point out that the device here investigated, differently than the configurations listed in Table III, is not yet configured as a practical sensor device, given that the main scope of this investigation was to determine key factors that may influence the measured parameters under hydrogen exposure. For practical embodiments, it is possible to optimize the device architecture with the use of, e.g., periodic hybrid lines or alternative Pd -based resonant structures, with potential to greatly improving the hydrogen detection limit.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a hybrid $Cu-Pd-Cu$ microstrip transmission line is employed to detect hydrogen. A low-cost planar design is implemented on a standard FR4 dielectric substrate, resulting in a simple device having a section of Pd for hydrogen detection. The Pd section is electrically connected to input and output copper microstrip transmission lines. The results attained show hydrogen detection is possible using the proposed low-cost implementation.

In addition, a detailed analysis was carried out to identify the main factors that could contribute to the device's response. From the analysis it was determined that hydrogen induced attenuation changes in the transmittance function would be negligible for the design parameters of the devices. It was also shown that field spreading within the palladium section can enhance the device sensitivity to hydrogen, but it also produces a high degree of insertion loss. By a semi-quantitative analysis of the spectral dependence of the transmittance function, one concludes that the existence of a high field mismatch in the copper and palladium sections of the device, can lead to high values of the reflection coefficient at each junction, and very small phase changes in this coefficient, due to hydrogen absorption of the Pd film, would be the most likely effect to produce a measurable variation in the device's transmittance.

The experimental results indicate that the microstrip device having a 20 mm long Pd strip could detect the presence of 1.6% hydrogen, and the best device response occurred around 3.2 GHz. A clear indication that the signal observed was due to hydrogen was demonstrated by comparing the response of

the devices to repeated exposure to hydrogen, relative to the variability in the spectrum for the device exposed to nitrogen.

The fact that ultrathin Pd films can be used to construct sensor devices with a reasonable response to hydrogen, is an important finding and it would not be expected on a first examination of the problem, from the point of view of the attenuation function alone, as discussed in the current work. Facilities that fabricate thick Pd films usually employ electroplating. Electroplating of palladium on patterned devices is not a standard low-cost procedure and it is hard to find facilities that can carry out specific configurations. On the other hand, fabrication of devices using ultrathin Pd films, by sputtering, or even by electron beam evaporation, can be easily implemented and large scale fabrication is possible.

It is important to point out that the current work is a proof of concept study and the device configuration at the present stage is not practical as a sensor device. With the goal of developing more practical, portable and low-cost sensor devices capable of detecting hydrogen with high detection sensitivity, based on the present work, resonant structures are being investigated capable of achieving higher sensitivity for hydrogen detection and that could prove as good candidates for patch antenna or RFID planar devices for wireless sensing.

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